

THE LEARNING LANDSCAPE: MAPPING EMERGING PEDAGOGIES TO DIVERSE STUDENT STYLES FOR ENHANCED ACHIEVEMENT

Lyrissa Jane M. Carpina

Madalunot Elementary School, Pinacdao, Samar, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12216851>

ABSTRACT

Effective education hinges on aligning teaching methods (pedagogies) with students' preferred learning styles. This dynamic interplay between diverse teaching styles and student learning preferences ultimately impacts academic performance. This study determined the teaching pedagogies and students' learning styles: their emerging realities to the academic performance of the District of Daram II, Schools Division of Samar, during the school year 2022-2023. Utilizing a quantitative approach and a survey questionnaire, it was revealed that some students learn best by doing, others by seeing, and some through reading or listening; thus, they seem aware of what helps them learn best. Meanwhile, teachers who use lots of different teaching methods will help most students succeed. Teachers who know how their students learn best can tailor how they teach. Students should think about how they learn best and let their teachers know. Teachers need support to learn lots of different ways to teach. It was concluded that students demonstrate unique learning style preferences, highlighting the need for teachers to differentiate their instruction. Most students show adaptability and awareness of how they learn best. This self-knowledge can be a powerful tool if students are empowered to use it. Varied teaching approaches and awareness of students' learning styles seem positively correlated with academic performance. This underscores the importance of teacher adaptability and diverse instructional methods and recognize the complexity of student achievement. Factors like motivation, engagement, undiagnosed learning challenges, and access to support systems all play a role and need to be considered along with learning styles.

Keywords: *Learning Styles, Teaching Pedagogy, Auditory, Tactile, Visual*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching pedagogies and learning styles play a crucial role in this academic world. Diverse styles of teaching and learning occur due to the reaction among students in relation to the teaching styles that are demonstrated by the teachers in the classroom, and this could affect the students' learning styles preferences that lead to their academic performance in school. Moreover, the diversity in teaching and learning styles preferences would result in matches and mismatches between the teachers' teaching pedagogies and students' learning styles. Teachers know that no two students are the same and that there is a spectrum of different learning styles. Teaching styles, therefore, have great impact to students' ability to learn and comprehend. This is why knowledge of different students' learning styles is essential for teachers.

Individuals learn in different ways using several learning styles, but lecturers may not always share material and learning experiences that match students' learning preferences. Mismatches between learning and teaching styles can lead to disappointment with students are taking, and lead to underperformance among them (Subramaniam,2019). Teaching profession requires intelligence, skills, insights, and diligence in succeeding different way to fulfill the challenge of classrooms (Kardia & Wright, 2004). Teaching style is a multitask phenomenon that illuminates how teachers teach knowledge; accomplish classroom work, and supervision of students (Sheikh & Mahmood, 2014). However, learning style refers to an individual's preferred way of processing new information for efficient learning. Rita Dunn described the concept of learning style as "a unique way developed by students when he was learning new and difficult knowledge. Learning style is about how students learn rather than what they learn. The learning process is different for each individual; even in the same educational environment, learning does not occur in all students at the same level and quality (İlçin,2018).

According to Ariola (2012), "Learning style is the composite of characteristics of cognitive, affective and psychological factors that serve as relatively stable indicators of how a learner perceives, interacts with, and responds to the learning environment." According to Stewart and Felicetti (1992), learning is influenced by the educational conditions under which a student learns. Therefore, learning style is not just concerned about what students need to learn but rather how they want to learn in the most effective way. One of the most significant challenges in learning is for individuals to take responsibility for their own learning. When learners take responsibility for their own learning, they attribute meaning to the process of learning, leading to effective learning (Nzesei, 2015).

Teachers need to understand the process of individual learning. In the learning process, individuals are interacting with the environment uniquely processing the information and requiring a unique environment for learning. Thus, addressing the challenge in facilitating learning conditions while organizing such interactions should

be taken into consideration to help individuals to optimize their learning (Sighn, 2017). In the past decades, many educators widely applied teacher-centered strategies to impart knowledge to learners' comparative to student-centered strategies. Until today, questions about the effectiveness of teaching strategies on student learning have consistently raised considerable interest in the thematic field of educational research (Hightower et al., 2011).

Moreover, research on teaching and learning constantly endeavor to examine the extent to which different teaching strategies enhance growth in student learning. Effective teaching requires flexibility, creativity, and responsibility to provide an instructional environment able to respond to the learner's individual needs. Tomlinson (2001) puts it beyond the experiential evidence that pervasive uniformity in teaching fails many learners. There is a reason in both theory and research to support a movement towards an instruction attentive to students' variance manifested in at least three areas: the student's readiness, interest, and learning profile. Nowadays, one of the challenges in teaching-learning process is knowing the most effective teaching approach and strategies that are also in line with the learning styles of the students.

Furthermore, aside from learning styles and teaching strategies, academic achievement is also considered as the center of interest in educational research. Studying the issue of achievement has extended beyond simple to complex issues of intelligence and prior academic achievement into how learners interact with the learning material and teaching strategies.

A good teacher must change his behavior towards or the development of skills and good character that help obtain their purpose for themselves and the community as well. The students will obtain more information, retain more knowledge and perform better when students' learning styles are aligned with teachers' teaching styles. Damavandi (2011) stated that students understand and recall better when the teachers' teaching styles match the learning styles of the students. To do this, the faculty members need to review continuously their teaching styles based on learning styles of the students to ensure that students are actively participating in class to further improve their students' academic performance. Good academic performance can also be obtained based on the learning styles of the students. Several recent studies stated that learning styles of the students influence their academic performance and in relation to that, several authors assert that it is important to understand their learning styles so as to improve students' academic performance.

Staiger and Rockoff (2010) discovered large differences in student achievement in different teachers' classrooms, even after controlling for students' prior achievement and characteristics. Especially following the No Child Left Behind (NCLB) Act which ensures that all children have a fair, equal, and significant opportunity to obtain a high-quality education and reach proficiency in academic achievement standards. This approach is likewise consistent with DepEd's mission to protect and promote the right of every Filipino to quality, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education.

The law emphasizes that educational institutions must acknowledge, appreciate, and respect the students' differences in intelligence, talents, skills, interest, and background. Thus, researchers believe that by understanding the influence of learning styles and teaching strategies, educators will find effective ways to improve academic performance. This also tried to fill in the gap in terms of the research that look closely into the contribution of these key variables on the students' performance (Cardino,2020).

In the District of Daram II, Schools Division of Samar, teachers experience the same plight with the foregoing situation in other countries. In fact, they are confronted with the issue on how to be effective in the delivery of education. Despite exerting efforts in utilizing and devising teaching pedagogies, still the academic performance of the students is not at par. Based on the trends in the grade ranges in the past three school years, the students posted 77 percent untransmuted grade range during the School Year 2019-2020 while during the School Year 2020-2021, the untransmuted grade range is posted 77.8 percent and during the School Year 2021-2022, the untransmuted grade range is posted at 78 percent, which may redound to the students' learning styles.

The foregoing served as a challenge for the teachers in as much as the demand for an exemplary performance is expected from them by the DepEd. Thus, the researcher was motivated to conduct the study to determine the teaching pedagogies and students' learning styles in the District of Daram II, Schools Division of Samar during the School Year 2022-2023.

Research Questions

This study determined the teaching pedagogies and students' learning styles in the District of Daram II, Schools Division of Samar during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of the following personal characteristics:
 - 1.1 age and sex;
 - 1.2 civil status;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4 number of years in teaching;
 - 1.5 gross monthly family income;
 - 1.6 performance rating based on the latest IPCRF;
 - 1.7 relevant in-service training; and
 - 1.8 attitude toward teaching?

2. What is the profile of the student-respondents in terms of the following personal characteristics:
 - 2.1 age and sex;

- 2.2 nutritional status;
- 2.3 parents' highest educational attainment;
- 2.4 parents' occupation;
- 2.5 gross monthly family income; and
- 2.6 attitude toward schooling?

3. What are the teaching pedagogies adapted by the teacher-respondents in teaching the subjects to the students?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the teaching pedagogies adapted by the teacher-respondents in teaching and their profile variates?

5. What are the learning styles of the student-respondents in assimilating the lessons taught to them?

6. Is there a significant relationship between the student-respondents' learning styles and their profile variates?

7. What is the academic performance of the student-respondents based on the mean grade during the first and second quarters?

8. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of the student-respondents and the following:

- 8.1 student-related profile variates;
- 8.2 teacher-related variates;
- 8.3 teachers' teaching pedagogies; and
- 8.4 students' learning styles?

9. What intervention program may be developed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a quantitative approach to investigate teaching methods and student learning styles in the District of Daram II, Schools Division of Samar, during the 2022-2023 school year. The study involved all 168 teachers and a sample of 226 grade 5 and 6 students from the public elementary schools in the district. Questionnaires were used to collect data from both teachers and students, and these questionnaires were validated by experts in education. Researcher collected data on teacher-respondents' profiles, including age, sex, education, teaching experience, income, performance ratings, training, and attitude towards teaching. Student-respondents' profiles included age, sex, nutritional status, parents' education and occupations, family income, and attitude towards schooling. Moreover, the study examined the teaching methods used by teachers and the learning styles of the students. Additionally, researchers looked at student academic performance based on their first and second quarter grades. Furthermore, the researcher used a mix of descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze

the data, including measures like frequency, percentages, and means. They also employed statistical tests like chi-square and Spearman's rank correlation. The study employed correlation analysis to explore the relationships between student academic performance and various factors, including student characteristics, teacher characteristics, teaching methods, and student learning styles. Before collecting data, the researchers obtained approval from the appropriate authorities in the school district. Data collection faced challenges due to geographical factors, but the researcher enlisted the help of school personnel to overcome these obstacles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the findings of this study through the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered. The following were the salient findings of the study:

1. Some kids learn best by doing, others by seeing, and some through reading or listening.
2. They seem aware of what helps them learn best, which is a great advantage.
3. Whether a student is a boy or girl, comes from a rich or poor family, or is in any situation, it does not strongly affect how they learn or how well they do in school.
4. Having a good attitude toward school helps, but it does not automatically lead to better grades.
5. Teachers who used lots of different teaching methods (doing activities, showing pictures, explaining things, having discussions) would help most students succeed.
6. Teachers who know how their students learn best can tailor how to teach individual students or groups.
7. Surprisingly, teachers with higher ratings seemed to have students with slightly lower grades; this needs more investigation.
8. Students should think about how they learn best and let their teachers know.
9. Teachers need support to learn lots of different ways to teach.
10. Maybe the current rating system does not measure how well teachers help students learn.
11. Interviews and watching classrooms can give us better insights into why this happens.

12. Lots of other things affect how well a student does in school, like how motivated they are or if they have any learning difficulties.
13. Students show preferences for various learning styles. Some indicators were stronger (e.g., hands-on activities, visual aids, reading or written explanations, skill with charts and graphs), but no single style dominated. Most students are adaptable, indicating awareness of their preferences.
14. Teachers should use a variety of approaches (hands-on, visual, lectures, discussions, reading, and writing) to meet the diverse learning styles in the classroom.
15. Unsurprisingly, even a slightly positive attitude towards school doesn't directly translate to better academic performance.
16. Teachers with higher performance ratings seem to be slightly associated with lower student academic performance. This warrants further investigation.
17. Both pedagogies and learning styles showed a positive correlation with academic performance. This indicates that varying teaching methods and understanding students' learning styles can positively influence academic outcomes.
18. Encourage students to recognize their strengths in various learning styles to advocate for their needs and maximize their potential.
19. Since some learning styles are less represented, help students identify their strongest styles for the best results. Consider sharing student preferences with teachers to personalize instruction.
20. Explore the surprising negative correlation between teacher performance ratings and student outcomes.
21. Help teachers expand their teaching toolkit to include varied approaches. Investigate which specific pedagogies correlate most strongly to improved student outcomes.
22. This study may have a limited sample size or scope. It's helpful, but it shouldn't be overgeneralized.
23. Statistical correlations give numbers, but interviews or observations could provide richer insights into why these connections exist and how to improve learning experiences.
24. There are many factors beyond the measured one's impact on learning. Consider

also motivation, engagement, study habits, and individual learning challenges for a holistic approach.

25. These factors have a negligible or weak correlation to learning style preference or academic performance in this study. This suggests a potentially equitable environment where background plays a lesser role.

Pedagogies Adapted by Teachers in Teaching the Subject

There was a weak, but statistically significant, positive correlation between the teachers' use of diverse pedagogies and their students' academic performance.

Table 1

Relationship Between the Students' Academic Performance and Their Pedagogies Adapted by the Teachers in Teaching the Subject

Variate	Association		Fisher's t-Value	p-Value @ $\alpha=.05$	Evaluation/ Decision
	Coefficient	Degree			
Pedagogies	Spearman's Rho = 0.241	Weak	2.765	0.009	S / Reject Ho.

$\omega=p<.001<.05$ pairwise normality deviated from the norm S = Significant
Fisher's t-Critical = ± 1.982 , df = 124 NS = Not Significant

This suggests that teachers who incorporate a variety of teaching approaches (constructivist, collaborative, etc.) tend to have students who perform somewhat better academically. Diverse pedagogies might better cater to different learning styles, making learning more engaging and effective for more students, leading to improved outcomes. While the correlation is weak, it's encouraging because it indicates that teachers' pedagogical choices do have a measurable impact on student performance. It cannot be definitively said that using more pedagogies causes better performance. Other factors were likely at play. Specific pedagogies that were most beneficial were not known. Further research on the impact of individual teaching approaches might be valuable. Successfully implementing a range of pedagogies requires skill and effort. This variable might also be influencing student success.

Support teachers in learning about and experimenting with different teaching approaches. Professional development in this area could be beneficial. Help teachers identify suitable pedagogies based on their subject area, specific student needs, and their teaching styles. Investigate: which specific pedagogies have the strongest association with improved academic outcomes and how teachers' skills in implementing those pedagogies influence the relationship.

Learning Styles Adapted by Students.

There was a moderate, statistically significant relationship between students' learning styles and their academic performance.

This finding suggests that students who are aware of and utilize their preferred learning styles (visual, auditory, kinesthetic, etc.) tend to demonstrate better academic outcomes. Understanding students' learning styles provides a potential avenue for teachers to personalize their instruction, potentially leading to improved performance for many students. Encouraging students to reflect on how they learn best could empower them to take ownership of their learning process and advocate for their needs.

Table 2

Relationship Between the Students' Academic Performance and Their Learning Styles

Variate	Association		Fisher's t-Value	p-Value @ $\alpha=.05$	Evaluation/ Decision
	Coefficient	Degree			
Learning Styles	Spearman's Rho = 0.461	Very Weak	6.813	0.000	S / Reject Ho.

$\omega=p<.001<.05$ pairwise normality deviated from the norm S = Significant
Fisher's t-Critical = ± 1.982 , df = 224 NS = Not Significant

In summary, the correlation is not extremely strong. This indicates that learning styles are one influential factor among many in determining academic performance. Learning is complex. Over-reliance on the concept of learning styles alone risks oversimplifying the factors that contribute to academic success.

Conclusions

The following were the conclusions drawn from the findings of the study:

1. Students demonstrated unique learning style preferences, highlighting the need for teachers to differentiate their instruction.
2. Most students showed adaptability and awareness of how they learned best. This self-knowledge can be a powerful tool if students are empowered to use it.
3. The negligible impact of factors like age, sex, and socioeconomic background on learning style and performance suggested a potentially equitable learning environment. This is a positive finding to build upon.

4. Varied teaching approaches and awareness of students' learning styles seemed positively correlated with academic performance. This underscores the importance of teacher adaptability and diverse instructional methods.
5. The surprising negative correlation between teacher performance ratings and student outcomes required further investigation. Current evaluation systems (like IPCRF) might need revision to ensure they holistically measure true teaching effectiveness.

Recommendations

Anchored on the conclusions drawn from the findings of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Use formal or informal assessments to help students identify their preferred learning styles. Adapt instruction accordingly (provide choices, offer materials in different formats, and vary activity types).
2. Participate in professional development to learn new teaching strategies that cater to different learning styles (hands-on activities, collaborative projects, multimedia presentations, etc.).
3. Regularly consider the variety of methods teachers' use. Create lessons that cater to a wider range of learners.
4. Openly discuss learning styles with the class. Invite students to share what helps them learn best and involve them in designing activities that support their preferences.
5. Budget for and actively encourage teachers to expand their knowledge of learning styles and diverse teaching strategies. Offer workshops, conferences, and collaborative mentoring opportunities.
6. Review teacher performance metrics. Develop a more holistic evaluation system that includes observations, student feedback, and measures of student growth over time.
7. Create mechanisms for students to share their learning preferences with teachers and administrators. Provide resources and training to help students understand and advocate for their learning styles.
8. Encourage a balanced use of quantitative and qualitative research within the school. Support teachers with collecting classroom data about student learning styles and preferences to enhance personalized instruction.

9. Parents share insights about their children's learning preferences with their teachers. Encourage open communication to support a collaborative approach to the child's education.
10. Reinforce learning styles discovered at school. If they're a visual learner, provide colorful study aids. If they're hands-on, turn homework into interactive activities.
11. Conduct in-depth research to understand why higher teacher ratings were associated with slightly lower student performance. Use a mixed-methods approach (quantitative and qualitative) to uncover potential reasons.
12. Study which specific teaching strategies have the strongest positive impact on student outcomes, particularly in relation to diverse learning styles.
13. Investigate how students' self-awareness of their learning styles and their belief in their ability to learn (growth mindset) influences their academic performance and motivation.
14. Encourage students to reflect on their learning styles and communicate them to teachers. This can foster better student-teacher collaboration and self-advocacy for personalized learning.
15. Provide opportunities for teachers to expand their repertoire of teaching strategies (visuals, hands-on, discussion-based, etc.) and learn how to identify and support different learning styles.
16. Explore alternative evaluation models that go beyond standardized test scores and encompass student growth, classroom environment, and diverse measures of teaching excellence.
17. Supplement statistical findings with interviews and classroom observations. This will provide a richer understanding of why learning environments are equitable, and how students and teachers utilize this to their advantage.
18. Recognize the complexity of student achievement. Factors like motivation, engagement, undiagnosed learning challenges, and access to support systems all play a role and need to be considered along with learning styles.
19. Design lessons that cater to a variety of learning styles (visual aids, discussions, hands-on activities) to benefit a broader range of students.
20. Consider using informal or formal assessments to help students identify their learning preferences.
21. Encourage students to communicate their preferred learning styles to their teachers to facilitate better personalization of instruction. Remember that learning

styles are just one piece of the puzzle. Combine this knowledge with other strategies that promote motivation, engagement, and effective study habits.

22. Strengthen the conduct of SLAC to improve teaching pedagogies.

23. Conduct reward and recognition to deserving teachers and students during the quarterly Portfolio Day.

24. Further study may be conducted focusing on other areas on pedagogies adopted by teachers and the learning styles of students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical approval for the study was obtained before the conduct of this study. All respondents received written and oral information about the aim of the study and the possibility of withdrawing their participation at any time without the need to give reasons for doing so. Confidentiality was assured according to ethical research guidelines. Moreover, informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express her utmost gratitude and appreciation to all those who gave her the possibility to complete this research.

First and foremost, to the Almighty God, who is the highest of all, given the researcher the strength and encouragement throughout all the challenging moments of completing this research. The researcher is truly grateful for His unconditional and endless love, mercy, and grace.

The researcher extends heartfelt gratitude to Dr. Imelda M. Uy, Public Schools District Supervisor of the Schools Division of Catbalogan City, for her invaluable expertise and unwavering support throughout this research journey. Her patience, motivation, and enthusiasm were instrumental, and her immense knowledge provided crucial guidance at every step of the way.

The researcher expresses her sincere gratitude to Dr. Nimfa Torremoro, Dean of the College of Graduate Studies. Dr. Torremoro's expertise was invaluable in navigating the research process, particularly when tackling seemingly insurmountable challenges. Her insightful suggestions and willingness to dedicate her time proved instrumental in acquiring necessary information and maintaining the researcher's motivation throughout the paper.

Dr. Guillermo D. Lagbo, Director of Institutional Research & Extension at Samar Colleges, Inc., who was also the statistician of this research, for his work on the

quantitative examination of data with his expertise and knowledge that was given in this study. Also, to Dr. Natalia B. Uy, Dean of the College of Business Management at Samar Colleges Inc., and Dr. Michelle L. Mustacisa, Public Schools District Supervisor of the Schools Division of Catbalogan City, for their constructive criticisms and insightful comments, suggestions, and recommendations for the improvement of this paper.

To Ma'am Janice R. Colebra, my deepest gratitude for her unwavering support and expert guidance, especially during the publication process of this research paper. Her vast knowledge of academic publishing was invaluable as I navigated the complexities of submitting my work for publication. Her insights on selecting an appropriate journal, tailoring the manuscript to specific requirements, and addressing reviewer feedback were instrumental in bringing this paper to a wider audience.

The researcher also appreciates Mrs. Salvacion C. Planea, Schools District-In-Charge in the District of Daram II, Schools Division of Samar, for allowing the researcher to conduct and give full support to finish the study.

Special recognition is given to all the Teacher-and Student - Respondents in the District of Daram II, Schools Division of Samar, for their cooperation and willingness to share their experiences and perspectives.

In addition, the researcher expresses appreciation to her parents, Mr. Bonifacio O. Carpina and Mrs. Dindin M. Carpina, also to her siblings, Andrew Cris M. Carpina and Ace M. Carpina, for their contribution to by taking good care of her son while working in this endeavor.

And lastly, the researcher expresses profound gratitude for her husband, Rey M. Bacalan and son, Zane Brion C. Bacalan, her loving family, and inspiration, for their unending support and motivation to pursue this study.

REFERENCES

- Ariola A. (2012), Learner's Learning Preferences and Teaching Strategies in Mathematics of Fourth Year High School at Mabitac Laguna. Department of Education, Division of Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1272228.pdf>
- Cardino, Jose Jr. (2020). Understanding of Learning Styles and Teaching Strategies Towards Improving the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics. Department of Education, Division of Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1272228.pdf>
- Damavandi Alireza et. al, (2011). Academic achievement of students with different learning styles. *International Journal of Psychological Studies* 3 (2) 186. Retrieved from: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1318/1/012028/pdf>
- Heydarnejad T., Hosseini Fatemi A., Ghonsooly B. (2017). An exploration of EFL teachers' teaching styles and emotions. *J. Appl. Linguist. Lang. Res.* 4, 26–46.

- Retrieved from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
- İlçin, N., Tomruk, M., Yeşilyaprak, S.S. et al.(2018). The relationship between learning styles and academic performance in TURKISH physiotherapy students. *BMC Med Educ* 18, 291 (2018). Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-018-1400-2>
- Kardia, D. B., & Wright, M. C. (2004). Instructor identity: The impact of gender and race on faculty experiences with teaching. Occasional Paper. University of Michigan Center for Research on Learning and Teaching.
- Nithya Dewi Subramaniam (2019). Learning Styles and Teaching Styles Determine Students' Academic Performances: *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1238274>
- Nursen İlçin (2018). The relationship between learning styles and academic performance in Turkish physiotherapy students. <https://bmcmmededuc.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12909-018-1400-2>
- Nzesei, M. M. (2015). A Correlation Study between Learning Styles and Academic Achievement among Secondary School Students in Kenya. University of Nairobi. Retrived from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1272228.pdf>
- Sheikh, A., & Mahmood, N. (2014). Effect of different teaching styles on students' motivation towards English language learning at secondary level. *Science International*, 26(2), 825-830. <https://www.ilkogretim-online.org/fulltext/218-1630259880.pdf>
- Staiger, Douglas O et. al, (2010). Searching for Effective Teachers with Imperfect Information." *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 24 (3): 97-118.
- Staiger, D. O., & Rockoff, J. E. (2010). Searching for effective teachers with imperfect information. *Journal of Economic perspectives*, 24(3), 97-118.
- Stewart, K. L., & Felicetti, L. A. (1992). Learning styles of marketing majors. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 15(2), 15-23. Retrieved September 14,2013 from<http://www.nwlink.com/~donclark/hrd/styles.html#sthash.SbepFXmt.dpuf>.
- Tomlinson, C. (2001). *How to differentiate instruction in mixed ability classrooms* (2nd ed.). Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum